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SPACE-BASED EARTH OBSERVATION IMAGERY & WARTIME ATROCITIES IN THE INTERNATIONAL LEGAL IMAGINATION

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the encounter between the legal gaze and Space-Based Earth Observation (SBEO) as a technoscientific medium that, in its content, informs the procedural work of international lawyers and, in its form, opens new possibilities for seeing and interpreting phenomena under international law. As the world's attention turns to conflicts in Sudan, Ukraine, and Israel-Palestine, the data derived from SBEO techniques and the subsequent 'sense-making' of technicians and jurists have become critical commodities in global sensory economies, delimiting what is visible and thereby legally actionable under international humanitarian and criminal law. Through its rhetorical capacity and sensory techniques, especially recent innovations in hyperspectral and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imaging, SBEO produces new ways of quantifying and visualising harm across temporal and spatial scales in these armed conflict zones, particularly for environmental and infrastructural damage. Through case studies of emerging legal proposals for the international criminalisation of 'ecocide', 'domicide', and 'urbicide', the article considers SBEO's contribution to the reimagining and qualification of atrocity crimes within the thresholds of international criminal law, as well as the relevance of academic scholarship and grassroots civilian science to these projects of international justice. In doing so, it contends that the technoscientific nature of SBEO and the increasingly legal character of work conducted by remote sensing researchers, civil society actors, and interdisciplinary scholars are bringing these domains into ever closer proximity, producing a diffuse and participatory landscape of legal imagination that reshapes formal and informal discourse within IHL and ICL alike.

KEYWORDS: Earth Observation, International Criminal Law, Satellite Imagery, Armed Conflict, Ecocide, Domicide, Legal Theory.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The leveraging of Space-Based Earth Observation (SBEO) imagery and remote sensing² for international legal purposes has been well documented in space law and humanitarian literature.³ Objectives range from routine monitoring of international agreements to the more sensationalist detection, investigation, and prosecution of international crimes⁴ and human rights violations.⁵ While legal scholarship has gradually acknowledged the power of the visual image to shape international legal narratives and responses,⁶ SBEO, as a technical practice, exemplifies a more complex and nuanced technoscientific tool that, in its content, informs the procedural work of international lawyers, and in its form opens new possibilities for seeing and interpreting phenomena under international law.

As the world turns its attention to armed conflict in Sudan, Ukraine, Israel-Palestine, and beyond,⁷ the data derived from SBEO techniques has become an increasingly critical commodity in what Fleur Johns calls ‘global sensory economies’. These economies are made up of networks of actors, technologies, infrastructures, and legal norms that produce, evoke, organize, and circulate ‘sensory data’ about the world. In turn, this dictates the distribution of today’s critical immaterial resources like attention, authority, and knowledge, as well as their material counterparts like money, bodies, and objects.⁸ It is

² Although the distinction is hardly made in scientific circles, Principle I(a) of the UN Principles Relating to Remote Sensing of the Earth from Outer Space of 1974 distinguishes remote sensing from Earth Observation (EO) in that its fundamental purpose is “improving natural resources management, land use and the protection of the environment”. This indicates that the various other applications of remote sensing, including the purposes discussed above that are of interest to this study, fall outside of this category and thus are not within the purview of the aforementioned UN Principles. EO, as an alternative category, broadly incorporates space-based remote sensing and ground-based in situ-derived information – hence the specification of SBEO for the purposes of this piece. See United Nations General Assembly. (1986, December 3). *Principles relating to remote sensing of the Earth from space* (Resolution 41/65, GAOR, 41st Session). Principle I(a). United Nations.

³ See generally Farfour, M. (2019). The role and use of satellite imagery for human rights investigations. In S. Dubberley, A. Koenig, & D. Murray (Eds.), *Digital witness: Using open source information for human rights investigation, documentation, and accountability* (Chap. 11). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/law/9780198836063.003.0011>. See also Savage N. (2024). Eyes in the sky usher in new era of law and order. *Nature*, 635(8037), S1–S3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-03593-x>.

⁴ Satellite imagery has already been admitted in cases at the International Criminal Court (ICC), International Court of Justice (ICJ), the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA) at The Hague, and International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY). See Wang, B. Y., Raymond, N., Gould, G., & Baker, I. (2013). Problems from Hell, Solution in the Heavens?: Identifying Obstacles and Opportunities for Employing Geospatial Technologies to Document and Mitigate Mass Atrocities. *Stability: International Journal of Security and Development*, 2(3), Art. 53.; See also Raymond, N. A., Card, B. L., & Baker, I. L. (2014). A nes: Developing standard remote sensing methodologies to detect and document mass atrocities. *Genocide Studies and Prevention: An International Journal*, 8(3), 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.5038/1911-9933.8.3.4>.

⁵ See Edler, R., Glasze, G., Kinzelbach, K., & Walker, B. B. (2025). Remote sensing analysis for documenting human rights violations in zones of armed conflict: A systematic review of empirical research. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2025.1603575>; See also Rapach, S., Riccardi, A., & Wheate, R. (2024). Earth observation technology’s alignment with OHCHR indicators for strengthening human rights breach investigations and adjudication. *Science & Justice*, 64(6), 710–727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scijus.2024.09.006>.

⁶ Joyce, D. (2010). Photography and the Image-Making of International Justice. *Law and Humanities*, 4(2), 229–249.

⁷ In addition to the listed conflicts, sovereign use of force has been employed in Venezuela, Iran, Lebanon, Bahrain, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Kuwait, Oman, Iraq, Azerbaijan, Syria, Jordan, and Cyprus since the original time of writing. See also Hak, J. W., & Rewald, S. K. (2024, July 1). *The satellite era: How Earth observation data is being mobilized as potential digital evidence*. *EJIL: Talk! (Blog of the European Journal of International Law)*. <https://www.ejiltalk.org/the-satellite-era-how-earth-observation-data-is-being-mobilized-as-potential-digital-evidenc/>.

⁸ Johns, F. (2017). Data, Detection, and the Redistribution of the Sensible in International Law. *American Journal of International Law*, 111(1), 57–103. doi:10.1017/ajil.2016.4.

according to these economies that technicians and jurists alike can ‘make sense’ of worldly phenomena. International legal work maintains a specific and powerful ‘distribution of the sensible’, for example, the lexicon of war crimes itself serves as a common vocabulary that frames practices of warfare as matters of ‘international’ concern, and irrigates this concern towards an enumeration of sufferings they engender.⁹ Imagery, and documentary photography in particular, holds a special place as a singularly authoritative format for sensory data that transmits the affective and analytical sensation of witnessing a captured moment of reality. SBEO is situated at the intersection of documentary photography and cartography, another foundational structuring paradigm in international legal thought,¹⁰ and has developed techniques that go beyond photographic imagery to record, map, and visualise information like movement, depth, displacement, and more. While jurists are quite accustomed to discussing how law influences and governs imagery, thinking in terms of sensory economies allows us to examine how specific imaging techniques frame the legal gaze, and thus possibilities for legal action.

This piece intends to think sociotechnically about this interrelationship in the context of conflict-induced mass harms and atrocities to better ascertain how looking at the world through SBEO can inspire continuous reinterpretation in and of international humanitarian law (IHL) and international criminal law (ICL).¹¹ Through first taking a granular look at the encounter between the legal gaze and contemporary SBEO techniques like hyperspectral and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imagery, it then becomes possible to contextualise the production of legal ‘reimaginings’ of atrocities and their possible qualification under existing ICL thresholds. The central ‘reimaginings’ to be examined here are the proposed international crimes of *ecocide*, *domicide*, and *urbicide*, which refer to the wilful and wanton destruction of a natural environment, housing, and urban spaces, respectively. These terms, which have gained significant traction in legal discourse in the past decade, frequently raise the question of the effectiveness of remedying old problems through new crimes and protections under IHL and ICL. I seek to set this debate aside in order to examine instead a more foundational question: how SBEO, as a technoscientific medium, shapes the legal imagination from which such proposals emerge and through which they gain normative traction, notwithstanding the high legal thresholds that challenge their legitimate adoption into the international legal order.

In this way, this piece proposes that novel techniques of SBEO legitimize the evocation and circulation of these proposed mass atrocity crimes both as popular neologisms and as legal concepts through the virilization and quantification of large-scale harms. The technoscientific nature of SBEO and the increasingly legal character of work conducted by SBEO technicians, civil society researchers, and interdisciplinary scholars bring the domains of remote sensing and ICL into ever closer proximity. While an evaluation of the possible use or limitations of these techniques within the minutiae of international legal proceedings lies outside of this paper's scope, it draws attention to how SBEO is being mobilized by jurists and non-jurists alike in their advocacy of new or expanded frameworks of international criminal accountability. It is not the intention of this study to evaluate the suitability of proposed or existing crimes vis-à-vis ongoing conflicts, but rather their character and instrumentalization in legal discourse.

To that end, the article proceeds in three parts. The first section takes a broad to narrow approach, first establishing the theoretical framework of encounter between the legal gaze, the legal imagination, and SBEO as a technoscientific medium to trace the interrelationship of novel ways of seeing. This is

⁹ Mignot-Mahdavi, R. (2024). War crimes as vocabulary shaping the visible. *Saint Louis University Law Journal*, 68(2), 277–292. <https://hal.science/hal-05382162>.

¹⁰ Lythgoe, G. (2023). Eradicating the exceptional: The role of territory in structuring international legal thought. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 1-18. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0922156523000675>.

¹¹ See generally Johns, F. (2023). *Help: Digital humanitarianism and the remaking of international order* (Online ed., Oxford Academic, 23 Feb. 2023); Nesiiah, V. (2003). Placing international law: White spaces on a map. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 16; Hill, G. (2021). The map and international law’s stifled visual discourse. *European Journal of Legal Studies*, 13.

followed by a more material examination into innovative SBEO techniques such as SAR, InSAR, and hyperspectral imagery, and the bearing that their specific epistemic and rhetorical properties have for the global sensory economy of armed conflict and the legal imagination. The second section turns to three substantive legal ‘reimaginings’ closely related to SBEO, examining in turn the proposed crimes of ecocide, domicide, and uricide. Analysis of the nature and applications of SBEO used in legal discourse regarding ongoing violent conflicts instantiates its role in rendering visible and legally cognisable the widespread, long-term, and severe destruction of environments, homes, and urban spaces, and in doing so pushes the thresholds of IHL and ICL. The final section reflects on the broader implications of this encounter for the broader space and technology legal research agenda, centering law, SBEO, the legal imagination, and warfare within a singular interdisciplinary and transnational normative conversation that demands theoretical and technical engagement from this generation of international jurists.

2. SPACE-BASED EARTH OBSERVATION & THE LEGAL GAZE

2.1. *From the Legal Gaze to the Legal Imagination*

The gaze, one of the more popular proposals from 20th-century phenomenology, is the figurative practice of looking and perceiving the world in a specific manner in accordance with given social dynamics and narratives, underpinned by a network of power-knowledge relationships on an institutional scale.¹² For international jurists, the legal gaze interprets the world suspiciously,¹³ seeking truth (or perhaps simply satisfactory resolutions) regarding complex, worldly, and sensory phenomena through categorisation into subjectivities, linked through obligations and rights. Lawyers are not blind to the spectacle of warfare, and bear witness both professionally and privately to visual media and numeric representations of violence. Such objects upon which one sets their gaze, and the techniques through which one ‘sees’, determine what ‘sense’ or knowledge can be derived therein. The complexity and diversity of modern technoscientific tools proliferate documentary techniques that render these objects legible in different ways, generating and framing visual fodder for the legal gaze.

It is not only where this gaze meets but rather where it *chafes* against its technoscientific sensory lenses that is of interest to this piece. This is an encounter of critical epistemic importance, in that it obligates the jurist to reconcile an observable sensory phenomenon with their own insufficient legal categories through the adaptation of the latter.¹⁴ The perception and quantification of atrocity-level harms to, for example, the aerial, terrestrial, and maritime environment, invites jurists to consider the capacity of international law to address these events and, where unsatisfactory, propose new creative interpretations of its corpus. It is precisely this intellectual computation that constitutes an act of legal imagination. Martti Koskenniemi understands such imagination to not be abstract, cerebral work, but rather the practical re-assembly and reinterpretation of existing legal materials in the pursuit of particular aims.¹⁵ Like reason, faith, or utopia, imagination is an instrument in the international jurist’s toolbox that can be deployed in the production of international legal concepts.¹⁶ This jurist is, nevertheless, circumscribed by existing legal language, concepts, and framework, as well as prefigured norms of credibility. Imagination is not an autopoietic,

¹² See notably *Discipline and punish: the birth of the prison* (1977) and *The birth of the clinic: an archaeology of medical perception* (1973).

¹³ Kennedy, D. (2014). The Hermeneutic of Suspicion in Contemporary American Legal Thought. *Law and Critique*, 25(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10978-014-9136-6>.

¹⁴ Sheila Jasanoff offers a clear example of this in her discussion of biomedical techniques for fetal medicine and coma care, which created new states of being between life and death that required legal adaptation, through legal imagination. See Jasanoff, S. (1995). *Science at the Bar: Law, Science, and Technology in America*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjz822j>.

¹⁵ Koskenniemi M (2021) *To the uttermost parts of the earth: legal imagination and international power 1300–1870*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

¹⁶ Simpson, G. (2019). "Chapter 26: Imagination". In *Concepts for International Law*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing. 413-421. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474684.00031>.

inventive power but comes from within and proceeds by passing through new technologies that ‘de-form’ it, dismantling categories, releasing possibilities, and expanding the range of political experience, per Walter Benjamin.¹⁷

As this impetus is rhetorically wieldable yet materially conditioned, it is worthwhile to turn to the question of the metaphorical meeting point of the legal and the technoscientific. The application of such technologies is rarely divorced from IHL and ICL efforts – in fact, they often focus on the same subjects, events, and geographical areas of interest to jurists, and in doing so reciprocally inform law’s methodological approaches, and *vice-versa*. Zones of armed conflict offer the most apt illustration of this interdisciplinary juncture, as the asymmetry of sensory economies becomes particularly evident in the context of emergencies, where extracted data from concerned locations takes on the greatest value for the greatest number of consumers, including lawyers.¹⁸ The spectacle of conflict and destruction¹⁹ is imbued with an urgency that obliges states and the international commercial space sector to concentrate onto these areas the most advanced observational techniques at their disposal. It is this technoscientific mediation by and through SBEO satellites and computational practices that (in)visibilises certain features and sensory contours of violent conflict,²⁰ upon which jurists and conflict scholars set their literal and metaphorical gaze.

2.2. *New Ways of Seeing through SBEO*

The global legal architecture for the use of SBEO in international justice remains patchwork at best. The seminal article of the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and other Celestial Bodies* of 1967 legitimises SBEO on the basis of the principles of freedom of space exploration and use, with meaningful consequences: while unauthorised aerial EO of a sovereign territory is subject to international air law and thus can be lawfully restricted,²¹ SBEO over that same territory cannot, enabling satellite operators to capture what might not otherwise be disclosed by states. Despite ambiguous standards for admissibility, the probative value and relevance of such imagery is generally recognised by international courts,²² although this has only ever concerned optical imagery for corroboratory and not necessarily dispositive evidence, meaning that it has only ever been considered in combination with ‘ground truth’ data.

While the non-binding *UN General Assembly Principles Relating to Remote Sensing of the Earth from Outer Space* of 1986 do confirm a right of ‘sensed’ states to non-discriminatory access to primary and processed data at a reasonable cost²³ in accordance with binding space law,²⁴ state practice and *opinio juris* has since deviated substantially from the main guiding principles on international cooperation and the free flow of data. This deviation primarily manifests in the form of restrictive national licensing regimes, data-sharing regulations, and export controls that prohibit certain space technologies and optical

¹⁷ Benjamin, W. (1996). *Imagination*. In M. Bullock & M. W. Jennings (Eds.), *Selected writings, volume 1, 1913–1926* (pp. 280–282). Harvard University Press. For a discussion of the intersection of Benjamin’s theory and legal imagination for humanitarian mapping, see Johns, F. (2023). *Digital humanitarian mapping and the limits of imagination in international law*. *Law and Critique*, 34(3), 341–361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10978-023-09361-6>.

¹⁸ Johns, F. (2025). *Palliative presentism and its alternatives: International legal emergencies via digital interfaces*. *European Journal of International Law*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chaf035>.

¹⁹ Bakogianni, A., & Hope, V. M. (2015). *War as spectacle: Ancient and modern perspectives on the display of armed conflict*. Bloomsbury classical studies monographs. London; New York: Bloomsbury Academic. ISBN 9781472522290.

²⁰ Johns, *supra* note 18.

²¹ International Civil Aviation Organization. (1944). *Convention on International Civil Aviation* (Chicago Convention), Art. 1. <https://www.icao.int/publications/pages/doc7300.aspx>.

²² See Wang, et al. *supra* note 4.

²³ United Nations General Assembly, *supra* note 2 at Principle XII.

²⁴ Notably the obligation of due regard enshrined in Principle IX of the OST and the UN Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space of 1976.

resolutions, and subject satellite operators and downstream users to government permission for use or dissemination of SBEO data. This often depends on the ‘sensitivity’²⁵ of the data collected, the availability of the data on the market or lack thereof,²⁶ and specific imagery of national security²⁷ or geopolitical²⁸ importance. ‘New Space’ private firms have increasingly taken centre stage in the commercial defense sector and the global sensory economy writ large by offering SBEO data at a frequency, speed, and quality often unmatched by larger publicly-owned constellations. Procurement of these commercial services by militaries not only fuels legal conundrums around the status of dual-use technologies²⁹ but also further limits already costly access to imagery through contractual limitations³⁰ and state influence.³¹

Although multispectral imagery remains the predominant format of SBEO, several novel techniques constitute important advancements that change how end-users employ satellite imagery in their respective activities. The most noteworthy include SAR and hyperspectral imagery, which underpin high-resolution 3D digital elevation models, moving target indication, structural damage assessment, interferometry, environmental composition, and more. While multispectral imagery captures essentially the equivalent of a photograph, hyperspectral imagery can identify the material and chemical properties in that same photograph, including vegetation and mineral make-up. Much excitement is also directed towards the application of active, radar-based systems that, unlike passive optical systems, are not dependent on solar light and are thus capable of capturing images at any time, and can penetrate through cloud cover, smoke, and several meters of materials like foliage and soil. By emitting and receiving the backscatter of its own radio waves, SAR-equipped satellites always collect data in the same conditions, facilitating

²⁵ For example, see the German policy on remote sensing data at Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology. (2008, April 15). *German national data security policy for space-based Earth remote sensing systems: Background information for the Act on Satellite Data Security (Satellitendatensicherheitsgesetz – SatDSiG)*. <https://www.bmwi.de/>.

²⁶ For example, see the U.S. licensing policy at U.S. Department of Commerce National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (2020, May 20). *Licensing of Private Remote Sensing Space Systems*. Federal Register. 85(98). 30790–30815. <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2020-05-20/pdf/2020-10703.pdf>.

²⁷For example, India’s recent restrictions on sensing of military bases and major oil refineries. See Govt bans mapping and export of sensitive locations under data regime (2022, September 27). *Business Standard*. https://www.business-standard.com/article/economy-policy/govt-bans-mapping-and-export-of-sensitive-locations-under-data-regime-122092700144_1.html.

²⁸ A noteworthy extraterritorial case of this is Section 1064 of U.S. National Defense Authorisation Act of 1997 (Public Law 104-201), better known as the Kyl-Bingamen Amendment, which heavily restricts the collection or dissemination of satellite imagery of Israel-Palestine by American operators. In 2020, the permitted resolution was lowered from 2 to .40 meters based on the accessibility of such imagery through non-U.S. operators, however the new standard is still not considered sufficient for most major analytic activities. See generally Zerbini, A., & Fradley, M. (2018). *Higher Resolution Satellite Imagery of Israel and Palestine: Reassessing the Kyl-Bingaman Amendment*. *Space Policy*, 45, 43–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.03.002>.

²⁹ See notably Azcárate Ortega, A. (2023, June 5). *Not a Rose by Any Other Name: Dual-Use and Dual-Purpose Space Systems*. *Lawfare*. <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/not-a-rose-by-any-other-name-dual-use-and-dual-purpose-space-systems>; J. P. Bennett, C. (2025). The dual-use conundrum of the Lisbon Treaty regarding space governance: Solutions through international legal interpretation? *Global Policy*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.70029>.

³⁰ For example, the business model of Vantar (formerly Maxar) and its procurement contract with the U.S. government allowed the latter to buy outright the proprietary rights to certain images, notably those over the Gaza Strip, thereby precluding access to any other potential customers. See NPR. (2023, November 16). *What satellite images over Gaza reveal about [sic] Israel’s intentions*. <https://www.npr.org/2023/11/16/1212889717/satellite-images-us-israel-gaza>.

³¹ Business & Human Rights Resource Centre. (2023, November 7). *Palestine: Key providers of satellite images have begun to restrict imagery of Gaza*. <https://www.business-humanrights.org/fr/derni%C3%A8res-actualit%C3%A9s/palestine-satellite-image-companies-restrict-obscure-images-of-gaza/>.

multi-temporal change detection for continuous moving target characterisation³² and Interferometric SAR (InSAR), a geodetic technique that collapses multiple SAR images into a surface map that indicates up to millimetre-scale ground surface deformations over the course of days to years. In other words, InSAR allows for the mapping of ground deformation through the rapid comparison of different radar images of the same area, which can identify and calculate the velocity of moving objects, or the extent of damage to a given location.

Although these technologies have been around for more than half a century, it is the convergence of several key contemporary material and politico-juridical affordances³³ that have made them accessible to a wider public : Miniaturised constellations have made compacting the size and multiplying the number of SBEO satellites commercially feasible on a massive scale;³⁴ for radar imagery that is not visually legible in the way its optical counterpart is, the recent bounds in artificial intelligence (AI) for data processing has been a tremendous catalyst for its uptake among users;³⁵ and the growing ubiquity of information communication technologies and open data initiatives of the 2010s³⁶ enabled widespread access and experimentation with these techniques. While fast and high-quality, commercial SBEO quickly becomes cost prohibitive for the study of rapidly changing conflict environments and has obligated many non-state actors to focus on improving interpretative techniques for medium-quality open-access SBEO from the U.S. Landsat and E.U. Copernicus constellations.³⁷ This has led to a proliferation of scholarly and grassroots efforts demonstrating creative approaches to open-source SBEO analysis of conflict-induced phenomena conducted by groups like Forensic Architecture,³⁸ Conflict Ecology,³⁹ and Bellingcat⁴⁰ with significant legal and counter-mapping implications. In this way, the circle of individuals engaged in acts of witnessing, interpretation, and advocacy of legal questions under IHL and ICL expands to include civilian non-jurists⁴¹ who nonetheless have a stake in the collective international legal imagination.

2.3. SBEO Image-ination

The innovative SBEO techniques discussed in the previous section are exemplary illustrations of change in technoscientific framing: SAR and its processing methods allow viewers to see beyond the

³² Bai, J., & Qu, W. (2025, May 28). Overview of video synthetic aperture radar moving target detection algorithms. In *International Conference on Remote Sensing, Mapping, and Image Processing (RSMIP 2025)* (Vol. 13650, 1365012). SPIE. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3067758>.

³³ James J. Gibson's term here refers to the possibilities an environment offers, provides, or furnishes to the individual. See J. J. Gibson (1966). *The Senses Considered as Perceptual Systems*. Allen and Unwin, London.

³⁴ Davie, O. (2025, May 24). *The satellites using radar to peer at Earth in minute detail*. BBC Future. <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20240524-the-satellites-using-radar-to-peer-at-earth-in-minute-detail/>.

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ For more details on the interesting history of the beginning of open satellite data policies, see Zhu, Z., Wulder, M. A., Roy, D. P., Woodcock, C. E., Hansen, M. C., Radeloff, V. C., Healey, S., Schaaf, C., Hostert, P., Lymburner, L., Pahlevan, N. (2019). Benefits of the free and open Landsat data policy. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 224, 382-385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.02.016>.

³⁷ Sticher, V., Wegner, J. D., & Pfeifle, B. (2023). Toward the remote monitoring of armed conflicts. *PNAS nexus*, 2(6), pgad181. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgad181>.

³⁸ Forensic Architecture is a research agency based at Goldsmiths University London whose work has been admitted before courts in the U.S., U.K., Germany, Greece, Israel, Guatemala, Colombia, presented to the European Court of Human Rights, UN General Assembly, and the ICC where it is a member of the Technical Advisory Board. See <https://forensic-architecture.org/>.

³⁹ Conflict Ecology is a geospatial research lab based at Oregon State University. Its work has been published in *The New York Times*, *the Washington Post*, *Al Jazeera*, *the Financial Times*, *the BBC*, *the Guardian*, *Der Spiegel*, *Bloomberg News*, among other scholarly journals. See <https://www.conflict-ecology.org/>.

⁴⁰ Bellingcat is an independent collective of researchers, investigators, and citizen journalists focused on open-source investigations into war zones, human rights abuses, and criminal activities and has been awarded several prestigious international awards for their work. See <https://www.bellingcat.com/>.

⁴¹ See Wang, et al. *supra* note 4.

immediately visible present – often rendered into visceral before/after juxtapositions⁴² – into multi-temporal and multi-spatial dimensions. Remote sensing scholars have noted a significant “[...] paradigm shift away from change detection, typically using two points in time, to monitoring, or an attempt to track change continuously in time” through the combination of coherent change detection methods and dense time series analysis.⁴³ SAR-derived analysis can likewise capture ground and object displacement and map them onto digital elevation models that paint a larger picture of the spatial density of damages and the widening contours of front lines.⁴⁴ These approaches broaden and diversify the kinds of land surface change, like ground moisture and building destruction, that can be continuously observed and thus acted upon. These new ways of seeing pull into sharp focus nuanced features of the visual world: human and non-human displacement, air and water pollution, urban morphology of war zones, agriculture, the structural integrity of infrastructure, biodiversity, tempo and intensity of violence, and more.

What demands consideration, however, is not only the content of SBEO’s sensory data, but the relevance of SBEO’s own unique format to legal thought. This brings us to the nexus of technology, law, and the imagination, which has become a meaningful site of international legal discourse⁴⁵ on how law is imagined by jurists and increasingly non-jurists, and how law itself imagines the world through datafied, algorithmic, and digital prisms. The notion of ‘sociotechnical imaginaries’ allows legal scholars to trace how technoscientific developments that influence collective perceptions of public good and desirable futures⁴⁶ also shape the way in which that law defines its subjectivities and social functions.⁴⁷ This proposal is fundamentally one of co-production of knowledge and social ordering, for the sciences and the law alike.⁴⁸ For this reason, SBEO is pivotal to the (co-)production of the legal imagination, both figuratively and etymologically, as it provides a visual image and largely informs how jurists should read it. Satellite imagery carries certain narratives about its relationship to the world, particularly its veracity, that attract the legal gaze and embed themselves in legal hermeneutical strategies. As has been argued previously,⁴⁹ the sociotechnical narratives attached to outer space have played a role in the co-production of the conceptual underpinnings of today’s broad corpus of space law. In this same way, the SBEO of

⁴² Auchter, J. (2025). Visualizing War through Satellite Footage: Technological Capacity, Truth, and the View from Above. *Media, War & Conflict*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/17506352251350329>.

⁴³ Woodcock, C. E., Loveland, T. R., Herold, M., & Bauer, M. E. (2020). Transitioning from change detection to monitoring with remote sensing: A paradigm shift. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 238, Article 111558. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111558>.

⁴⁴ Van Den Hoek, J. (2021). The City is the Medium and Satellite Imagery Are a Prism. In *Urban Remote Sensing*, X. Yang (Ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119625865.ch15>.

⁴⁵ Brännström, L., Noll, G., Parsa, A., et al. (2024). Guest editorial: Tech and the transformation of legal imagination. *AI & Society*, 39, 103–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01727-9>.

⁴⁶ Jasanoff, S., & Kim, S.-H. (Eds.). (2015). *Dreamscapes of modernity: Sociotechnical imaginaries and the fabrication of power*. University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/D/bo20836025.html>.

⁴⁷ Jasanoff, S., & Kim, S.-H. (Eds.). (2015). *Dreamscapes of modernity: Sociotechnical imaginaries and the fabrication of power*. University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/D/bo20836025.html>.

⁴⁸ Jasanoff, S. (2004) ‘Ordering Knowledge, Ordering Society’, in Jasanoff S. (ed.), *States of Knowledge. The Co-Production of Science and Social Order*, pp. 13–45. London/New York: Routledge.

⁴⁹ Of note is Professor Matthew Craven’s piece on the construction of space as a ‘global commons’ in the Cold War political and technoscientific context, at Craven, M. (2019). ‘Other spaces’: Constructing the legal architecture of a Cold War commons and the scientific-technical imaginary of outer space. *European Journal of International Law*, 30(2), 547–572. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chz024>. See also Rulier, F. (2023). X-15 et droit de l’espace : L’imaginaire technoscientifique dans la doctrine juridique spatiale des années 1950 et 1960 [X-15 and space law: Technoscientific imagination in space law’s doctrine in the 1950s and 1960s]. *Nacelles*, 14. <https://interfas.univ-tlse2.fr/nacelles/1951>.

war-related harms is imbued with several narratives capable of influencing a *collective* legal understanding of imagery, regardless of differing interpretations of content.

Notably, the ‘God’s eye-view’ through which one ‘sees’ projects a sense of epistemic authority that comes from the distance of the perspective and the technoscientific quality of the medium. As Lisa Parks observed, “[...] because of its remoteness and abstraction, the satellite image functions as an overview of the war, and it draws upon the discursive authority of meteorology, photography, cartography and state intelligence to produce its reality and truth effect”⁵⁰. This sense of objectivity translates into indisputability – the idea that an image can ‘speak for itself’. Particularly when the gaze is set upon a spectacle of violence, there is often a concurrent spectacle of the secret that engrosses one in uncovering what is otherwise obscured, whether that be mass graves in Srebrenica or a tarp-covered decoy submarine in Sevastopol.⁵¹

Figure 1. SAR image of Sevastopol Bay, Crimea, from 20 August 2024, following a Ukrainian missile attack, identifying the damaged Rostov-on-Don submarine as well as the presence of a possible decoy submarine under camouflage netting.⁵²

Subsequently, the perception of SBEO as a method of rational truth-telling means that it takes on a legitimising, persuasive, even testimonial quality: SBEO *reveals*, it *pinpoints*, it *geolocates*, it *confirms*, etc. What distinguishes SBEO as a rhetorical tool from other non-space-based technoscientific documentation is fundamentally its scale. The inclination, according to which the greater the magnitude of something, the greater its importance, represents a potent rhetorical tool; Mapping an oil spill, a city razed to the ground, or wildfire fallout renders visible the spatial scale of a phenomenon.⁵³ What goes

⁵⁰ Parks L (2001) Satellite views of Srebrenica: Televisuality and the politics of witnessing. *Social Identities* 7(4): pp. 593. DOI: 10.1080/13504630120107728.

⁵¹ Cartwright, J., Peterson, K., Gillet, Q., & Radzik, P. (2025, June 26). *Advanced SAR processing with Dwell mode: Enhancing situational awareness for defense and security in war zones*. Presented at ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025, Vienna, Austria. ICEYE. <https://lps25.esa.int/lps25-presentations/presentations/1306/>.

⁵² *Ibid.*

⁵³ It is noteworthy that this rhetoric of scale is sometimes applied to regardless of the scale of the actual image – this is observable in newspaper headlines that emphasise an episode of violence as “visible from space”, often not in pursuit of communicating the geographical scope of the episode but rather alluding to its human-level severity. For example, see Monetta, S. (2025, Oct. 30). Visible from space, bloody sands expose the slaughter of tens of thousands in Sudan. *NBC News*. <https://www.nbcnews.com/world/africa/sudan-africa-civil-war-rapid-support-forces-el-fasher-massacre-rcna240708>.

unspoken is the layered subjective and computational mediation of SBEO, as “[...] satellite imagery [is] always also the product of purposeful practices and interpretational uncertainties”,⁵⁴ especially for more complex techniques like InSAR. It is for these reasons that SBEO must be understood not as objective truth but rather as “a prism for reality”⁵⁵ that nevertheless can multiply the lenses with which the legal gaze can observe wartime atrocities and imagine pathways to remedy.

3. SPACE-BASED EARTH OBSERVATION & REIMAGINING ATROCITY CRIMES

3.1. Two ‘-cides’ of the Same Coin

The international legal vocabulary operates as a nebulous assemblage of terms that, in being written down, spoken aloud, and traded between jurists in a “[...] state of fierce competition for persuasiveness and semantic authority”, constitute the commodities of a textual economy of law.⁵⁶ One of the most accessible points of entry to the *vogue* of the legal semiotic market is neologisms, which illuminate not only the aesthetics⁵⁷ but the idealist objectives of legal scholarship at a given moment. Accompanying the re-emergence of large-scale warfare in the West (where the geographic focus of the international legal vision is often, if not teleologically,⁵⁸ focused), scholarly attention has been directed with renewed vigour to the legal vocabulary for atrocities in ICL, and therefore where it is the most productive to bridge this lexical phenomenon with that of SBEO.

In an effort to record, quantify, and taxonomise diverse forms of violence in armed conflict, jurists have employed neologisms to give a semiotically commodifiable form to new legal conceptions of mass harm. The proliferation of ‘-cide’ derivations,⁵⁹ e.g. ecocide, domicide, scholasticide, spaciocide, medicide, memoricide, etc., speaks to efforts to capture the variegated contours of international atrocities and reinvigorate the potentiality of ICL for analysis and norm-creation.⁶⁰ The efficacy and saliency of this terminology remain contested among scholars,⁶¹ principally due to the fact that ICL and IHL protective measures already encompass the material preoccupations of these concepts under the umbrella of ‘civilian objects’. Article 8(2)(b)(iv) of the Rome Statute prohibits the intentional launching of attacks in the knowledge that it will cause incidental loss of life or injury to civilians, damage to civilian objects, or widespread, long-term and severe damage to the non-human environment which would be clearly

⁵⁴ Olbrich, P., Witjes N. (2015) Earth Observation and International Security: The Role of Uncertainty in Satellite Imagery Analysis by Non-State Actors. *ESPI Perspectives*, No. 72. Vienna: European Space Policy Institute.

⁵⁵ Van Den Hoek, *supra* note 44.

⁵⁶ D’Aspremont, J. (2012). Wording in International Law. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 25(3), 575–602. doi:10.1017/S0922156512000283.

⁵⁷ Terms that might be considered neologisms are rarely ever purely autopoietic or autogenetic – jurists are inspired by and pull from the vocabularies of neighbouring disciplines, historical epochs, and legal regimes, hence the frequent adoption of Latin legal concepts (e.g. *erga omnes*, *jus cogens*, etc.) in international law.

⁵⁸ This is an argument of profound importance being advanced by scholars of the post-colonial and Third World approaches to international law (TWAIL) movements.

⁵⁹ It is important to note that, besides the clear etymological link to the term ‘genocide’, proponents of the listed neologisms do not necessarily suggest that these concepts be made legally equivalent to the crime of genocide, due in part to the high thresholds for attribution mentioned previously. Proposals have been made for incorporation into the list of crimes against humanity at the international level, and advocacy efforts focused on inclusion into domestic criminal law frameworks have shown success (see notes 81-84).

⁶⁰ Burgis-Kasthala, M., & Masetti Placci, M. (2024, November 14). Lost for words, yet grasping for neologisms: Gaza, genocide and the discursive limits of international law. *EJIL: Talk!* <https://www.ejiltalk.org/lost-for-words-yet-grasping-for-neologisms-gaza-genocide-and-the-discursive-limits-of-international-law/>.

⁶¹ See Dumont, A. (2024, May 7). *To cide or not to cide – Ecocide, what have you started? On new crimes and old problems in international law.* Völkerrechtsblog, <https://voelkerrechtsblog.org/to-cide-or-not-to-cide-ecocide-what-have-you-started/>.

excessive in relation to the concrete and direct overall military advantage anticipated.⁶² The legal thresholds enumerated here are problematic and substantially limit the prosecution of wartime damages – in short, the proportionality standard ultimately allows civilians and their objects to be trampled underfoot by the endlessly flexible exception of ‘military necessity’, application is limited to *international* armed conflicts, the *mens rea* element and reasonable military commander standard for ‘knowledge’ is highly subjective, and the *actus reus* element remains vague.⁶³ Prosecution of such harms as a crime against humanity⁶⁴ or genocide⁶⁵ faces similarly obscure and high thresholds that have been critiqued by States parties⁶⁶ to the Geneva Conventions, international lawyers,⁶⁷ atrocity scholars,⁶⁸ and ICJ judges themselves.⁶⁹

The quantification of warborne harm is a fraught affair – calculation and qualification of the scale, scope, proportionality and intent under the aforementioned thresholds is intensive and legally grey. It is for these reasons that SBEO imagery figures prominently as a key evidentiary and narrative technology in the critical repertoire of jurists in the evaluation of existing and proposed atrocity crimes.⁷⁰ For example, despite little guidance on the qualification of ‘*widespread, long-term, and severe*’ harm, references to

⁶² Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, Article 8(2)(b)(iv) (2002, amended 2021). <https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/2024-05/Rome-Statute-eng.pdf>. See also Art. 50, 51, and 147 of the Geneva Conventions I, II and IV, respectively, and Art. 52 (1), 35 (3), and 55 (1) of Additional Protocol I.

⁶³ Heller, K. J., & Lawrence, J. C. (2007). *The limits of Article 8(2)(b)(iv) of the Rome Statute: The first ecocentric environmental war crime*. *Georgetown International Environmental Law Review*, 20. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=979460>.

⁶⁴ Some have argued that the systematic destruction of the environment, civilian infrastructure, and dwellings can result in the forced displacement of civilian populations under the crimes of deportation or forcible transfer of population, or ‘other inhumane acts’ laid out by Art. 7(1)(d) and (k) of the Rome Statute. This implies a similar material (i.e. widespread or systematic) and mental (i.e. knowledge of the attack and the relevance of their action) element thresholds to war crimes, but there is no requirement of a specific targeted group, and therefore a (somewhat) less complex *mens rea* threshold, unlike for the crime of genocide.

⁶⁵ Prosecution of large-scale harms to the infrastructural, environmental, medical, and agricultural fabric of a zone of armed conflict as a crime under Art. 2 of the Genocide Convention has been proposed under subsection 3, in that the deliberate infliction of conditions of life to a national, ethnical, racial, or religious group calculated to bring about its physical destruction in whole or in part, as well as the imposition of measures intended to prevent births within the group under subsection 4. Individual criminal liability elements include the oft-discussed *dolus specialis* and the group condition, while State responsibility for genocide has additional thresholds including the ‘only reasonable inference’ standard from ICJ jurisprudence in *Croatia v. Serbia* and *Bosnia v. Serbia*.

⁶⁶ See notably the Joint Declaration of Intervention of Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom of 15 November 2023 before the ICJ on the Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide in Gambia v. Myanmar, <https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/178/178-20231115-wri-01-00-en.pdf>.

⁶⁷ See notably Tzouvala, N. (2024, June 24). *Genocide and political economy: Reconstructing the relationship*. Law & Political Economy Project. <https://lpeproject.org/blog/genocide-and-political-economy-reconstructing-the-relationship/>; See also Margale, S. (2025, July 3). *Genocidal intent revisited: Collective erasure vs. individual annihilation*. *Cambridge International Law Journal: Blog*. <https://cilj.co.uk/genocidal-intent-revisited-collective-erasure-vs-individual-annihilation/>; Essawy, R. M. (2024, May 3). *The attainability of the evidentiary standard for genocidal intent in Gaza*. EJIL: Talk! <https://www.ejiltalk.org/the-attainability-of-the-evidentiary-standard-for-genocidal-intent-in-gaza/>.

⁶⁸ See notably Gurmendi Dunkelberg, A. (2025). How to Hide a Genocide: Modern/Colonial International Law and the Construction of Impunity. *Journal of Genocide Research*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623528.2025.2454739>.

⁶⁹ Trindade, C. (2016, 18 April). Dissenting Opinion of Judge Cançando Trindade. Concerning the *Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (Croatia v. Serbia)*, Judgment. para. 467. <https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/118/118-20150203-JUD-01-05-EN.pdf>.

⁷⁰ El-Shawa, S., & Rotola, G. (2025, October). *Earth Observation for Justice in Gaza: Ethical and Legal Implications*. 76th International Astronautical Congress (IAC), Sydney, Australia. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17449136>.

historical ‘widespread’ harm cited impact areas of between 8,000-25,000 sq km⁷¹ – modern public satellites can easily capture 35,000-84,100 sq km⁷² in one image; ‘Long-term’ in ICL is often discussed in decades,⁷³ and recent studies not only conduct time series analysis decades into the past,⁷⁴ but project impact into the future;⁷⁵ ‘Severity’ is tied to damage prejudicing the health or survival of the population and environment,⁷⁶ and InSAR damage assessment techniques combined with deep learning and other *in situ* evidence have identified and mapped damaged facilities to estimate the extent of impact on critical infrastructure and nearby populations.⁷⁷

Figure 2. A display of the most common observation characteristics from a sample of SBEO literature on conflict and human rights published between 2006-2023.⁷⁸

Tracing the interplay between the legal imagination of mass harms and the rapid advancements in SBEO technologies requires examining their overlapping concern with conflict-related infrastructural damage and environmental consequences (see Figure 2). This is best done through a comparison of the conceptual frameworks and discursive mobilisation of the proposed concepts of *ecocide*, *domicide*, and *urbicide*.

⁷¹ International Committee of the Red Cross. (1978). *Official Records of the Diplomatic Conference of Geneva of 1974–1977* (Vol. XIV, CDDH/III/SR.26, p. 237).

⁷² Sentinel Hub. (n.d.). *Sentinel-2 L2A* (API documentation). <https://docs.sentinel-hub.com/api/latest/data/sentinel-2-l2a/>.

⁷³ International Committee of the Red Cross. (1978). *Official Records of the Diplomatic Conference of Geneva of 1974–1977* (Vol. XV, CDDH/215/Rev. I, para. 27).

⁷⁴ See Chidodo, S., Zhang, L., Zarei, A., & Feger, K.-H. (2025, June 19). *Remote sensing-based assessment of four decades of land use/land cover change in the Sigi River Watershed, East Usambara Mountains, Tanzania*. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2025.1594331>.

⁷⁵ See Murphy, M., Sharpe, E., & Huang, K. (2024). The promise of machine learning in violent conflict forecasting. *Data & Policy*, 6, e35. doi:10.1017/dap.2024.27.

⁷⁶ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2020). *Guidelines on the protection of the natural environment in armed conflict: Rules and recommendations relating to the protection of the natural environment under international humanitarian law, with commentary* (Updated ed.; originally published 1994) (para. 72, p. 38). <https://www.icrc.org/en/document/guidelines-protection-natural-environment-armed-conflict>.

⁷⁷ Hou, Z., Qu, Y., Zhang, L., et al. (2024). War city profiles drawn from satellite images. *Nature Cities*, 1, 359–369. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44284-024-00060-6>.

⁷⁸ Edler et al. conducted a review of 51 empirical case studies across 48 publications that used SBEO analysis of events in conflict zones with discussion of related human rights and IHL frameworks. Edler et al., *supra* note 5.

3.2. Ecocide

Ecocide can be understood as “[u]nlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts”.⁷⁹ Originally proposed in reflection of the environmental manipulation and devastation of the Vietnam War,⁸⁰ ecocide has been criminalised in several national⁸¹ and regional⁸² legal regimes, and submitted by certain States parties⁸³ to the ICC for adoption under the Rome Statute. The ICC has demonstrated an appetite for elaborating doctrine for international environmental crimes, building on Art. 8(2)(b)⁸⁴ but, so far, meaningful criticism of the pitfalls of the definition and (in)compatibility of ecocide for the previously noted thresholds reflects the uncertainty of future development.⁸⁵ This sentiment is contrasted by the public momentum for the concept,⁸⁶ which is only further fuelled by innovations in remote sensing technologies that have allowed civil society groups and researchers to access scientific evidence of large-scale environmental harms⁸⁷ through techniques that can map the interaction of warfare with agriculture, forestry, wildlife, and biodiversity.⁸⁸ SBE0 applications include the rapport between conflict and Normalised Difference Water Indexes, deforestation,⁸⁹ cropland

⁷⁹Independent Expert Panel for the Legal Definition of Ecocide. (2021, June). *Commentary and core text* (Article 8 ter). Stop Ecocide Foundation. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5ca2608ab914493c64ef1f6d/t/60d7479cf8e7e5461534dd07/1624721314430/SE+Foundation+Commentary+and+core+text+rev+6.pdf>. This is not the only definition for ecocide but is frequently cited in scholarship and international advocacy.

⁸⁰ Falk, R. A. (1973). Environmental Warfare and Ecocide – Facts, Appraisal, and Proposals. *Bulletin of Peace Proposals*, 4(1), 80–96. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44480206>.

⁸¹ Vietnam, Uzbekistan, France, Russia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Georgia, Belarus, Ukraine, Moldova, Armenia, Chile, and Belgium have all implemented legislation explicitly criminalising ecocide.

⁸² See European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2024, March 13). *Directive (EU) 2024/1203 on the protection of the environment through criminal law and replacing Directives 2008/99/EC and 2009/123/EC*. Official Journal of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/1203/oj>.

⁸³ Harvey, F. (2024, September 9). *Pacific islands submit court proposal for recognition of ecocide as a crime*. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/law/article/2024/sep/09/pacific-islands-ecocide-crime-icc-proposal>.

⁸⁴ Agence France-Presse. (2024, February 8). *ICC prosecutor wants court to try ‘environmental crimes’*. France24. Retrieved from <https://www.france24.com/en/live-news/20240207-icc-prosecutor-wants-court-to-try-environmental-crimes>.

⁸⁵See Bothe, M., Bruch, C. E., Diamond, J., & Jensen, D. (2010). International law protecting the environment during armed conflict: Gaps and opportunities. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 92(879), 569–592. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1816383110000427>; Heller, K. J. (2021, June 23). *Skeptical thoughts on the proposed crime of “Ecocide” (That isn’t)*. *Opinio Juris*. <https://opiniojuris.org/2021/06/23/skeptical-thoughts-on-the-proposed-crime-of-ecocide-that-isnt/>.

⁸⁶ It has notably been mobilised in the context of the Russo-Ukrainian war, with the EU and President Volodymyr Zelensky advocating for the prosecution of the 2023 destruction of the Kakhovka dam by Russia and the resulting flood disaster as a war crime. See European Parliament (2023, June 15). *European Parliament resolution on the sustainable reconstruction and integration of Ukraine into the Euro-Atlantic* (2023/2739(RSP)). Section H(4). *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/C/2024/490/oj/eng>.

⁸⁷ Nabil, A. (2019, May 16). Proof of Ecocide: Towards a Forensic Practice for the Proposed International Crime Against the Environment. *Journal of Archaeological and Environmental Forensic Science*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1558/aeefs.36378>.

⁸⁸ Zwijnenburg, W., & Ballinger, O. (2023). Leveraging emerging technologies to enable environmental monitoring and accountability in conflict zones. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 105(924), 1497–1521. doi:10.1017/S1816383123000383.

⁸⁹ Daiyoub, A., Gelabert, P., Saura-Mas, S., & Vega-García, C. (2023). War and deforestation: Using remote sensing and machine learning to identify the war-induced deforestation in Syria 2010–2019. *Land*, 12(8), 1509. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12081509>.

abandonment and farmer displacement⁹⁰ and starvation,⁹¹ and forest cover and peace negotiations,⁹² among others. Notably, open platform initiatives for continuous monitoring of war-induced environmental damage allow the collaborative elaboration of a body of knowledge that jurists can draw upon.⁹³

Figure 3. A representation of the transformation of the ecology of the northern part of Myanmar's Rakhine State over the course of the Myanmar civil conflict.⁹⁴

What is brought into the line of sight of the legal gaze in these assessments is not only a more granular texture of the environment-conflict nexus, but the gravity of the harm and the evidentiary significance of the information advanced.⁹⁵ In their examination of visual advocacy in the criminalisation of ecocide, Bertram and Hill noted that “[t]he ‘widespread’ character of ecocidal destruction and the scales implicated by this harm lend themselves to the removed vantage point of drone or satellite images. [...] [n]arrowing the case for ecocide by zooming right into specific scenes – or at least specific biomes –

⁹⁰ See Hazaymeh, K., Al-Omari, A., Alzoubi, O., & Al-Nawafleh, A. (2022). A remote sensing-based analysis of the impact of Syrian crisis on agricultural land abandonment in Yarmouk River Basin. *Sensors*, 22(10), 3931. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22103931>.

⁹¹ See Olsen, V. M., Fensholt, R., Olofsson, P., Bonifacio, R., Butsic, V., Druce, D., Ray, D., & Prishchepov, A. V. (2021). The impact of conflict-driven cropland abandonment on food insecurity in South Sudan revealed using satellite remote sensing. *Nature Food*, 2(12), 990–996. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00417-3>.

⁹² Bautista-Céspedes, O., Morales, M., & Armenteras, D. (2021). The effects of armed conflict on forest cover changes across temporal and spatial scales in the Colombian Amazon. *Regional Environmental Change*, 21, 80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-021-01770-6>.

⁹³ See notably the work of Forensic Architecture on ecocide in Indonesia and Gaza ; Zoï Environment Network. (2023). *Ecodozor platform for monitoring war-related environmental damage and risks in Ukraine*. <https://zoinet.org/product/ecodozor/>.

⁹⁴ Aung, T.S. (2021). Satellite Analysis of the Environmental Impacts of Armed-Conflict in Rakhine, Myanmar. *Science of The Total Environment* 781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146758>.

⁹⁵ This is already a phenomenon in motion for much domestic environmental litigation. See for example Zhang, Q., Guo, C., & Lv, J. (2025). Satellite Remote Sensing as a Powerful Tool to Review Evidence in Two Environmental Judicial Cases. *Environmental Forensics*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15275922.2025.2578494>.

makes for a more relatable claim to international criminality.⁹⁶ It is the broad range of possible scales and interpretative techniques that allow SBEO to slide along this spectrum of probative possibility, simulating the ability to zoom in and out of the world from above.⁹⁷ The ICRC and others have argued that the door is very much open for the ICC to exercise flexibility in their interpretation of the *mens rea* element,⁹⁸ proportionality, and widespread, long-term, and severe thresholds based on new scientific understandings.⁹⁹ The epistemic potential of SBEO imagery and other non-visual techniques for this purpose constitutes a development of extreme importance for the next generation of national and international criminal proceedings.

3.3. Domicide & Urbicide

While the notions of domicile and urbicide differ in their focal harm,¹⁰⁰ they nevertheless draw upon the same legal tenets and SBEO techniques in the construction and defence of their proposals. Urbicide refers to mass violence that aims to destroy an urban hub not necessarily as a strategic objective, but as a social-identity objective in a larger cultural genocide; despite its absence from the formal international legal lexicon, it figures greatly in the work of the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia and recent discourse on the urbanisation of contemporary warfare.¹⁰¹ Domicide, as advocated by the UN Special Rapporteur,¹⁰² is “[t]he deliberate destruction of homes, the rendering of homes uninhabitable or any other systematic denial of housing such as acts carried out in violation of international law and committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack against any civilian

⁹⁶ Bertram, D., & Hill, G. (2024). Polar bears and gavels: Visual advocacy in the criminalization of ecocide. *Journal of International Criminal Justice*, 22(1), 185–210. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jicj/mqae014>.

⁹⁷ See Part 3.2 for discussion on the limits of techno-optimism for ICL.

⁹⁸ In light of scholarly criticism of the direct and indirect intent rule of *mens rea* per Article 30 of the Rome Statute that both fail to effectively encapsulate the most serious of environmentally destructive acts, including those resulting from corporate practices, some jurists have developed creative proposals for the derogation and reinterpretation of the rule for a crime of ecocide, based instead on negligence, recklessness, and wilful blindness. See for example Savard, C. (2025). What *mens rea* for ecocide in the Rome Statute? *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642987.2025.2552468>.

⁹⁹ See Sharma, R. (2025, January 16). *Ecocide as the fifth international crime: Is the Rome Statute compatible with ecocide?* *Völkerrechtsblog*. <https://voelkerrechtsblog.org/ecocide-as-the-fifth-international-crime/>.

¹⁰⁰ While both the destruction of civilian individual and cultural property can be considered as a war crime under Art. 8(2) of the Rome Statute, advocacy for these concepts tend to focus on its criminalisation either as a crime against humanity or as a standalone crime like that of genocide, the most salient example being the UN Special Rapporteur Balakrishnan Rajagopal’s report on the right to adequate housing during violent conflict (see note XXXXXXXX). When a part of a widespread or systematic attack against a civilian population, housing destruction that results in displacement may qualify as the crimes of deportation or forcible transfer of population under Art. 7(1)(d) of the Rome Statute, or when conducted in a discriminatory or targeted way impacting a specific group can fall under crimes of persecution or apartheid under Art. 7(1)(h) and (j), and Art. 7(2)(g) and (h) respectively.

¹⁰¹ Robichez, Juliette. (2024). "Urbicide" and the preservation of the cultural heritage of humanity: solution to adapt international humanitarian law to the urbanization of war? [“Urbicídio” e preservação do patrimônio cultural da humanidade: solução para adaptação do Direito Internacional Humanitário à urbanização da guerra?]. *Brazilian Journal of International Law*, 21(1), 12-32.

¹⁰² Professor Rajagopal is an active advocate of imaginative, collective, and bottom-up methods of international law-making as a part of the TWAIL movement. See, for example, Rajagopal, B. (2003). *International law from below: Development, social movements, and Third World resistance*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511494079>. See also The Architectural League (2024, June 4). *Architecture, Planning, and International Law: On Domicide*. Featuring Balakrishnan Rajagopal (United Nations) and Natasha Aruri (UR°BANA), moderated by Brad Samuels (SITU). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-rdhHKh9-ak>.

population.”¹⁰³ Both of these proposals take on a relational concept of space¹⁰⁴ that emphasises the intimate link between the significance of space and human interaction – here advocating a shift from a materially static conceptualisation of the loss of individual and collective property towards a “[...] multidimensional view of home that spans different temporalities, affective registers and modalities of loss” that collapses diverse forms of destruction like dispossession, eviction, genocide,¹⁰⁵ forced displacement, demolition, and population transfer into a single notion.¹⁰⁶

Figure 4. Mapping of InSAR-identified structural damage in the Gaza Strip between October 2023 and January 2024 produced by Conflict Ecology and the Decentralised Damage Mapping Group.¹⁰⁷

Following improvements to AI-based techniques and open access to SAR data, researchers have taken to adapting InSAR methods traditionally used for natural disaster damage assessment to conflict settings, refining parameters for severity and scalability from cities to entire state territories.¹⁰⁸ Studies on

¹⁰³ Rajagopal, B. (2022, July 19). *Report of the Special Rapporteur on adequate housing as a component of the right to an adequate standard of living, and on the right to non-discrimination in this context: The right to adequate housing during violent conflict* (UN Doc. A/77/190, p. 14). United Nations.

¹⁰⁴ Harvey, D. (2006). Space as keyword. In D. Harvey, *Spaces of global capitalism: Towards a theory of uneven geographical development* (pp. 119–148). London: Verso.

¹⁰⁵ In the International Court of Justice’s recent order recognising Palestinian’s right to be protected from genocide underlines the link between the destruction of the home and genocide as evidenced by their mention of ‘home’ eight times in a 29-page document. See International Court of Justice. (2024, January 26). *Order in the case concerning Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (South Africa v. Israel)*. <https://www.icj-cij.org/node/203447>.

¹⁰⁶ Zeffert, H. (2024). Nowhere home. *London Review of International Law*, 12(2), 131–153. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lril/lrae013>.

¹⁰⁷ Bliss, L. (2024, January 24). *MapLab: Mapping Gaza’s destruction* [Newsletter]. Bloomberg News. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/newsletters/2024-01-24/maplab-mapping-gaza-s-destruction>.

¹⁰⁸ Sticher et al., *supra* note 37.

structural damage across Ukraine,¹⁰⁹ the Gaza Strip,¹¹⁰ Darfur in Sudan,¹¹¹ and in Mosul¹¹² and Syria¹¹³ have identified sites of damage and corresponding severity, patterns of destruction, and tempos of hostilities. Information like that contained in *Figure 4* is actively being taken up by international jurists, for example, regarding *jus ad bellum* proportionality assessment, for which they advance SBE0 InSAR data as evidence of a violation of proportionality through excessive harm and, crucially, domicile.¹¹⁴

Conflict damage itself contains many temporalities that are difficult to capture, as traditional methods continuously direct attention to large, abrupt damages, presupposing a permanence to damage from ephemeral events that are temporally distinct from the conflict at large¹¹⁵. Over time, their apparent presence can be erased through debris removal, muddled by rainfall or vegetation, or be repeatedly rebuilt and destroyed.¹¹⁶ These nuances to the spacio-temporal morphology of conflict damage make the collection and evaluation of evidence for criminal prosecution difficult, damage claims, and postwar re-appropriation. This was the case, for example, in the proceedings between the nomadic Bedouin Al-Turi families and Israel, which does not recognise their claims to property in the Negev region nor the existence of the village of Al-Araqib, and as such considers Bedouin villagers to be illegal trespassers and

¹⁰⁹ See Scher, C. & Van Den Hoek, J. (2025, June). Nationwide conflict damage mapping with interferometric synthetic aperture radar: A study of the 2022 Russia–Ukraine conflict. *Science of Remote Sensing*, 11(100217). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2025.100217>; Xu, H., Barbot, S., & Wang, T. (2024). Remote sensing through the fog of war: Infrastructure damage and environmental change during the Russian-Ukrainian conflict revealed by open-access data. *Natural Hazards Research*, 4(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nhres.2024.01.006>; Huang, Q., Jin, G., Xiong, X., Ye, H., & Xie, Y. (2023). Monitoring urban change in conflict from the perspective of optical and SAR satellites: The case of Mariupol, a city in the conflict between RUS and UKR. *Remote Sensing*, 15(12), 3096.

¹¹⁰ See Asi, Y., Mills, D., Greenough, P. G., et al. (2024). “Nowhere and no one is safe”: Spatial analysis of damage to critical civilian infrastructure in the Gaza Strip during the first phase of the Israeli military campaign, 7 October to 22 November 2023. *Conflict and Health*, 18, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-024-00580-x>; Kahraman, F., Imamoglu, M., & Ates, H. F. (2016). Battle damage assessment based on self-similarity and contextual modeling of buildings in dense urban areas. In 2016, *IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)* (pp. 5161-5164). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2016.7730345>; Scher, Corey & Van Den Hoek, Jamon. (2025). *Active InSAR monitoring of building damage in Gaza during the Israel-Hamas War*. 10.48550/arXiv.2506.14730.

¹¹¹ See Knoth, C., Slimani, S., Appel, M., & Pebesma, E. (2018). Combining automatic and manual image analysis in a web-mapping application for collaborative conflict damage assessment. *Applied Geography*, 97, 25-34; Knoth, C., & Pebesma, E. (2017). Detecting dwelling destruction in Darfur through object-based change analysis of very high-resolution imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 38(1), 273-295; Marx, A. J., & Loboda, T. V. (2013). Landsat-based early warning system to detect the destruction of villages in Darfur, Sudan. *Remote sensing of environment*, 136, 126-134.

¹¹² See Fakhri, F., & Gkanatsios, I. (2021). Integration of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data for change detection: A case study in a war conflict area of Mosul city. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 22, 100505; Bolorani, A. D., Darvishi, M., Weng, Q., & Liu, X. (2021). Post-war urban damage mapping using InSAR: the case of Mosul City in Iraq. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(3), 140.

¹¹³ See Braun, A. (2018). Assessment of building damage in Raqqa during the Syrian civil war using time-series of radar satellite imagery. *GI Forum 2018*, 6, 228-242; Lubin, A., & Saleem, A. (2019). Remote sensing-based mapping of the destruction to Aleppo during the Syrian Civil War between 2011 and 2017. *Applied geography*, 108, 30-38; Marx, A. J. (2016). Detecting urban destruction in Syria: A Landsat-based approach. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 4, 30-36; Tapete, D., & Cigna, F. (2016, August). Urban remote sensing in areas of conflict: TerraSAR-X and Sentinel-1 change detection in the Middle East. In *Fourth International Conference on Remote Sensing and Geoinformation of the Environment (RSCy2016)* (Vol. 9688, pp. 657-664). SPIE.

¹¹⁴Ulbricht, B., Weiner, A. S., Van Den Hoek, J., & Scher, C. (2025, June 5). “There is nothing left”: *Jus ad bellum* proportionality and Israel’s war against Hamas in Gaza. Stanford Public Law Working Paper. Forthcoming in the Berkeley Journal of International Law. SSRN : <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5283689>.

¹¹⁵ Van Den Hoek, *supra* note 44.

¹¹⁶ This applies for claims of returning displaced people as well. See Forensic Architecture. (2017, June 27). *Destruction and return in al-Araqib*. <https://forensic-architecture.org/investigation/destruction-and-return-in-al-araqib>.

has demolished their domiciles over 200 times.¹¹⁷ To this end, SAR and optical imagery evincing land-use patterns and the frequent damage¹¹⁸ to the village were advanced by the families as substantive proof of regular habitation and continuous seasonal land cultivation, as well as state responsibility for wrongful deprivation of private property resulting in forced displacement.¹¹⁹ SBEO was thus used to render visible, measurable, and legally actionable the protection of collective and private sites of human life.

Figure 5. Cumulative burden of infrastructure damage across the Gaza Strip and the spatial relationship of said damage to health, education, and water facilities between October 7 and November 22, 2023, produced by Conflict Ecology and the Decentralised Damage Mapping Group.¹²⁰

This relationship between time and space has special relevance for the proportionality and *mens rea* elements of international crimes. In a study of facilities demonstrating a high degree of damage clustering

¹¹⁷ Margalit, A. (2017). The Israeli Supreme Court and Bedouin Land Claims in the Negev: A Missed Opportunity to Uphold Human and Indigenous Rights. *International Journal on Minority and Group Rights*, 24(1), 57–69. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26557859>.

¹¹⁸ The village has been demolished 225 times since the 1950s, often multiple times a year, but is consistently rebuilt using temporary housing by the Bedouin communities. See Association France Palestine Solidarité. (2023, September 11). *Dans le Néguev/Naqab, le village bédouin d’Al-Araqib démoli pour les 220^e et 221^e fois*. <https://www.france-palestine.org/Dans-le-Neguev-Naqab-le-village-bedouin-d-Al-Araqib-demoli-pour-les-220e-et->

¹¹⁹ Forensic Architecture, *supra* note 116.

¹²⁰ Asi, Y., Mills, D., Greenough, P. G., *et al.* (2024). “Nowhere and no one is safe”: Spatial analysis of damage to critical civilian infrastructure in the Gaza Strip during the first phase of the Israeli military campaign, 7 October to 22 November 2023. *Conflict and Health*, 18, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-024-00580-x>.

for critical civilian infrastructure in the Gaza Strip in the first 46 days of Israel's Operation Iron Sword, researchers conducted a spatial inference statistic to characterise the randomness of this clustering, finding the resulting Z-scores as indicative of a <1% likelihood of the cluster damage occurring by random chance.¹²¹ They also calculate, according to the standards of the U.S. Methodology for Combat Assessment, that all governates fall within the category of 'completely destroyed' having suffered equal to or greater than 50% severe damage.¹²² In these calculations, there emerges an unspoken inverse statement regarding the margin of knowledge and intentionality of military decision-makers. Through these complex SBEO interpretative techniques, researchers are fundamentally engaging in legal questions of the proportionality and severity of Israel's conduct of hostilities. In doing so, they simultaneously propose a contextual schema for the evaluation of the 'systemic' or 'methodical' nature of violence as a crime against humanity, or the intent and knowledge thresholds of war crimes, as they could apply to a crime of domicile or urbicide.

3.4. Towards an Interdisciplinary Legal Imagination

The many prisms of SBEO techniques allow jurists to view and interpret sensory data of conflict-related damage in legally meaningful ways, extending new methods of characterising such damage across a spectrum of temporalities and geographical scales under existing and proposed atrocity crimes in ICL. This aligns with the broader paradigm shift in international legal theory away from anthropocentrism and toward a posthumanist conception of subjectivity that considers the non-human as well as the human,¹²³ and envisions universality as grounded in the interdependence and care of these relationships.¹²⁴

The illustrated *rapprochement* of SBEO techniques and legal imaginings for the appraisal of structural and environmental wartime damage demonstrates, without being self-incriminatory, a certain techno-optimist affinity across the legal and remote sensing disciplines.¹²⁵ Variations in space technology, remote sensing techniques, and imagery accessibility dictate the production and circulation of knowledge and epistemic authority within the international sensory economies around armed conflicts. While military and commercial actors possess the most advantageous positions in these economies, open-access geospatial datasets and no-code platforms have been foundational in innovating interpretative methods and democratising access to SBEO to academia and other investigative researchers. The growing body of literature on these concurrent phenomena gives shape and direction to two critical projects of international justice, i.e. ecocide and domicile/urbicide, that have a fundamentally open-access and participatory character, defined by crowdsourcing, transfer learning, open-source mapping, digital archiving, and other civilian science methods.¹²⁶ As machine learning becomes more prevalent in documenting conflicts, professional and civilian scholars have assumed a greater role in these efforts, creating unavoidable

¹²¹ *Ibid.*

¹²² U.S. Joint Chiefs of Staff. (2019). *CJCSI 3162.02: Methodology for combat assessment*. U.S. Joint Chiefs of Staff.

https://www.jcs.mil/Portals/36/Documents/Doctrine/training/jts/cjcsi_3162_02.pdf?ver=2019-03-13-092459-350.

¹²³ See notably Arvidsson, M., & Sjöstedt, B. (2023). Ordering human–other relationships. In *The Routledge handbook of international law and anthropocentrism* (1st ed., pp. 21–...). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003201120-8>; Lindgren, T. (2018). Ecocide, genocide and the disregard of alternative life-systems. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 22(4), 525–549. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3357214>.

¹²⁴ Zeffert, H. (2024). Nowhere home. *London Review of International Law*, 12(2), 131–153. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lril/lrae013>.

¹²⁵ See Van Den Meerdsche, D. (2024). International law and technology as a critical project: A collective reading. *European Journal of International Law*, 35(4), 963–970. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chae069>.

¹²⁶ See, for example, Cornebise, J., Worrall, D., Farfour, M., & Marin, M. (2018). *Witnessing atrocities: Quantifying villages destruction in Darfur with crowdsourcing and transfer learning*. In *Proceedings of AI for Social Good Workshop at NeurIPS 2018 (NeurIPS'18)*. <https://cornebise.com/julien/assets/pdf/cornebise2018witnessing.pdf>. See more generally Weir, D., McQuillan, D., & Francis, R. A. (2019). Civilian science: The potential of participatory environmental monitoring in areas affected by armed conflicts. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 191(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-019-7773-9>.

consequences for the validation of such documentation under traditional legal expertise.¹²⁷ Bridging the gap between legal and scientific epistemic communities can take the form of interdisciplinary collaboration for technical standard-setting, capacity-building initiatives, and continuous remote monitoring observatories.¹²⁸

Figure 6. User interfaces of open-source tools for mapping country-wide destruction in Ukraine.¹²⁹ and the Gaza Strip¹³⁰ based on SAR image time series mapped onto Google Earth Engine.

While important, the logistical and procedural questions of procuring and ensuring SBEO's admissibility and interpretation in the courtroom, or the nuances of its use for deterrence or detection, lie out of the scope of this piece. Instead, this foregoing analysis points to the legal arguments that are already being made, and not exclusively by lawyers, but by civil society, academia, and other technical entities engaged in an ongoing interdisciplinary and transnational normative conversation. This is not incidental to

¹²⁷ Edler et al., *supra* note 5.

¹²⁸ For more on such proposals see Sticher et al., Sou et al., and Scher & Van Den Hoek at *supra* notes 37, 77, and 110. See also Bennett, M. M., Van Den Hoek, J., Zhao, B., & Prishchepov, A. V. (2022). Improving satellite monitoring of armed conflicts. *Earth's Future*, 10, e2022EF002904. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022EF002904>.

¹²⁹ Dietrich, O., Peters, T., Sainte Fare Garnot, V., et al. (2025). An open-source tool for mapping war destruction at scale in Ukraine using Sentinel-1 time series. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 6, 215. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-025-02183-7>.

¹³⁰ Beirut Urban Lab. *Tracking the Urbicide in Gaza*. <https://beiruturbanlab.com/en/Details/1977>.

international law but constitutive of it, as the co-production of technoscientific and legal knowledge is precisely the mechanism through which new ways of seeing generate new possibilities for legal action.

This is of critical importance precisely because IHL and ICL, of all branches of international law, are particularly future and present-oriented, acting as a body of norms and terms to guide real-time decision-making to prevent and rectify mass harms, as well as render justice *post facto*. While an essential component of the international legal order, the world rarely holds its breath for formal deliberations and decisions by recognised legal authorities like the International Criminal Court or the International Court of Justice – rather, jurists and non-jurists alike are constantly engaged in formal and informal debates over the ongoing requalification of conflict and harm. Focusing scholarly attention on this mode of decentralised, active legal discourse illustrates how moments when IHL and ICL norms are argued to be at their weakest, such as moments of egregious violation, or slow to non-existent enforcement, are in fact when these norms are recentered, reaffirmed, and reimagined within popular discussion. To this point, InSAR analysis of damage clustering probabilities or hyperspectral capture of a frontline’s chemical fingerprint constitute a sensory image of warfare that participates in, informs, and frames these debates. In its capacity as a prism capable of attracting, refracting, and scaling the legal gaze, SBEO techniques lend legitimacy to participatory and expansive reimaginings of the international legal order’s formulations of universal crimes.

It thus follows that jurists cannot remain passive consumers of technical outputs. Engagement with the sociotechnical questions of interpreting SBEO data is not peripheral to legal work but internal to it: What is a standard ‘threshold of detectability’¹³¹ in pixels? What differences in coherence value distributions should trigger legal evaluation? How do limitations in SAR revisit cycles bear on narratives of systematic and continuous destruction? The quantification of harm is simultaneously a normative act, and the choice of which harms to render visible, at what resolution, and through whose interpretive frameworks, remains inescapably a legal and political one. Only through such engagement can the expanding sensory capacities of SBEO be aligned with the normative ambitions of IHL and ICL to render violence visible, to discipline its conduct, and ultimately to contribute to the prevention and redress of mass harm.

¹³¹ Weizman, E. (2017). *Forensic Architecture: Violence at the Threshold of Detectability*. MIT Press. Zone Books. ISBN 9781935408864.